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Handling Swarm of UAVs based on Evolutionary Multi-Objective Optimization

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Abstract The fast technological improvements in Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) has created new scenarios where a swarm of UAVs could operate in a distributed way. This swarm of vehicles needs to be controlled from a set of Ground Control Stations (GCSs), and new reliable mission planning systems, which should be able to handle the large amount of variables and constraints. This paper presents a new approach where this complex problem has been modelled as a Constraint Satisfaction Problem (CSP), and is solved using a Multi-Objective Genetic Algorithm (MOGA). The algorithm has been designed to minimize several variables of the mission, such as the fuel consumption or the makespan amongst others. The designed fitness function, used by the algorithm, takes into consideration, as a weighted penalty function, the number of constraints fulfilled for each solution. Therefore, the MOGA algorithm is able to manage the number of constraints fulfilled by the selected plan, so it is possible to maximize in the elitism phase of the MOGA the quality of the solutions found. This approach allows to alleviate the computational effort carried out by the CSP solver, finding new solutions from the pareto front, and therefore reducing the execution time to obtain a solution. In order to test the performance of this new approach 16 different Mission Scenarios have been designed. The experimental results show that the approach outperforms the convergence of the algorithm in terms of number of generations and runtime.

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1 Introduction

The fast and increasing development of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) capabilities has opened up new commercial applications for the industry. These new capabilities have opened new challenges to those classical computational intelligence methods that were used to manage the problems related to the operation of UAVs. These vehicles can be used in many domains such as surveillance [13], flight training [19], payload visualization [21] or disaster and crisis management, since they avoid risking human lives while their manageability permits to reach areas of hard access. Mission Planning for a team of UAVs involves generating tactical goals, commanding structure, coordination, and timing.

Nowadays, UAVs are controlled remotely by human operators from Ground Control Stations (GCSs), using rudimentary planning systems, such as following preplanned or manually provided plans. Traditional classic planners are based on a graph search or use a logic engine. But this kind of planners has several limitations, including the big computational cost that these algorithms need to solve for these missions. Even, problems related to replanning under uncertainty environments can generate serious problems to provide, in a short time, new possible solutions (plans) that can be used to solve unexpected problems during the mission execution. The plan operation usually takes into account only one UAVs due to the complexity of the problem, however the current trend is to involve these vehicles in a swarm of UAVs that need to be managed by a set of GCSs. This problem is known as Multi-UAV Cooperative Mission Planning Problem (MCMPP). MCMPPs have a lot of requirements that need to be considered in order to coordinate all the UAVs. These requirements generate search graphs that need huge process capabilities to find a solution.

Some modern approaches formulate the tactic mission planning problem as a Constraint Satisfaction Problem (CSP) [2]. A CSP consists of a set of variables (each one with its own domain) and a set of constraints restricting the values that variables can simultaneously take. So MCMPPs could be modelled as a CSP guided to find a correct schedule of UAV-task assignments.

In addition, Multi-UAV missions usually require the use of several GCSs for controlling all the UAVs involved. This generates a new Multi-GCS approach that makes the problem even more complex. Besides there are several parameters which can be used to define the quality of a solution, so an option to solve this type of problems could be using Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algorithms (MOEAs). Nevertheless, in some complex problems the search space is huge while the solution space is very reduced, so it is necessary to consider some new techniques in order to guide the algorithm and accelerate its convergence.

In this work, we have extended previous works [18,17] in order to design and implement a Multi-Objective Genetic Algorithm (MOGA) to solve the MCMPP. In this sense the fitness function has been designed to check the CSP model of the problem. So, if a solution fulfill all the constraints, then the fitness works as a Pareto-based function to optimize different quality parameters. On the other hand, when the solution checked is invalid, i.e. does not fulfill all the constraints, the fitness function has been extended following two approaches. In the first approach, the CSP check the constraints until some fail occur, and return the number of constraints fulfilled until this fail. This number is used in the optimization as a weighted penalty function, so the higher this number, the better the solution is. In the second approach, the CSP is forced to check all the constraints even if some fail occurs, and then it returns the number of constraints unfulfilled. Now, this number is used in the optimization as in the first approach, but inversely, so the smaller this number, the better the solution is. These heuristics intend to decrease the number of generations needed to converge to an optimal Pareto Optimal Frontier (POF) and, therefore, reduce the runtime of the algorithm as the experiments show.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Next section introduces some related works applied to the problem of Mission Planning and a background on Multi-Objective Optimization and MOEAs. Section 3 describes how a UAV Mission is defined using the CSP representation. Section 4 presents the hybrid MOGA-CSP algorithm developed with the new fitness functions considering the number of constraints. In Section 5 the new approach is tested against several mission datasets and compared with a previous approach. Last section presents the final analysis and conclusions of this work.

2 Related Works

2.1 Mission Planning Problems

In the literature there are some attempts to implement mission planning systems. Fabiani et al. [6] modelled the problem for search and rescue scenarios using Markov Decision Process (MDP) and solve it with dynamic programming algorithms. Leary et. al [10] compared the performance of Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP), Simulated Annealing (SA) and Auction Algorithms (AAs) for mission planning problems with multiple UAVs. Wang et al. [24] represented the task scheduling of UAVs as a MILP and used Tabu Search (TS) to solve this problem. Shang et al. [22] proposed a combination of Genetic Algorithms (GAs) and Ant Colony Optimizations (ACOs) for solving the UAV team orienting problem.

An essential concept in Mission Planning is cooperation or collaboration, which occurs at a higher level when various UAVs work together in a common mission sharing data and controlling actions together. There are few contributions that deal with Multi-UAV problems in a deliberative paradigm (cooperative task assignment and mission planning). Bethke et al. [3] proposed an

algorithm for cooperative task assignment that extends the Receding-Horizon Task Assignment (RHTA) algorithm to select the optimal sequence of tasks for each UAS. Another approach by Kvarnstrom et al. [9] proposes a new mission planning algorithm for collaborative UAVs based on combining ideas from forward-chaining planning with partial-order planning. This approach led to a new hybrid Partial-Order Forward-Chaining (POFC) framework that meets the requirements on centralization, abstraction, and distribution found in realistic emergency services settings.

Other works have been focused on distributed approaches for solving mission planning. Pascarell et al. [12] proposed a Core Paths Graph (CPG) algorithm for trajectory planning.

Finally, other approaches formulate the mission planning problem as a CSP, where the tactic mission is modelled and solved using CSP techniques [16, 7], in combination with Genetic Algorithms [18] or represented inside a distributed multi-agent system [8].

2.2 Multi-Objective Optimization Problems

Real-world optimization problems often require the solutions to meet multiple performance criteria (or objectives), simultaneously - these are known as Multi-Objective Optimization Problems (MOPs). These objectives are often conflicting, wherein an improvement in one objective cannot be achieved without detriment to another objective(s). In this case, there is no single solution to a MOP that can be selected objectively; rather a set of solutions exists, representing different performance trade-offs between criteria. A minimization MOP can be mathematically defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \min \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) &= (f_1(\mathbf{x}), f_2(\mathbf{x}), \dots, f_m(\mathbf{x}))^T \\ &\text{subject to } \mathbf{x} \in \Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)^T$ is a vector of n decision variables from the decision space Ω ; $\mathbf{f} : \Omega \rightarrow \Theta \subseteq \mathbb{R}^m$ consists of a set of m objective functions, and a mapping from n -dimensional decision space Ω to m -dimensional objective space Θ .

Definition 1 Given two decision vectors $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in \Omega$, \mathbf{x} is said to **Pareto dominate** \mathbf{y} , denoted by $\mathbf{x} \prec \mathbf{y}$, if:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\} \quad f_i(\mathbf{x}) &\leq f_i(\mathbf{y}) \\ \exists j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\} \quad f_j(\mathbf{x}) &< f_j(\mathbf{y}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Definition 2 A decision vector $\mathbf{x}^* \in \Omega$, is **Pareto optimal** if $\nexists \mathbf{x} \in \Omega$, $\mathbf{x} \prec \mathbf{x}^*$.

Definition 3 The **Pareto set** PS , is defined as:

$$PS = \{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega \mid \mathbf{x} \text{ is Pareto optimal}\} \quad (3)$$

Definition 4 The **Pareto front** PF , is defined as:

$$PF = \{\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) \in \mathbb{R}^m | \mathbf{x} \in PS\} \quad (4)$$

The goal of MOEAs is to move the non-dominated objective vectors towards PF (convergence), and also generate a good distribution of these vectors over the PF (diversity). There exists several approaches that have been designed for this purpose, including Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm-II (NSGA-II) [5], Strength Pareto Evolutionary Algorithm 2 (SPEA2) [28] or Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algorithm based on Decomposition (MOEA/D) [25], among others.

There are several approaches that treat with MOEAs in high complexity problems [26]. Some of these approaches have been used in the literature to solve planning and scheduling problems with multiple objectives. Mittal et al. [11] used NSGA-II for the UAV path planning problem, where the length of the curve and the risk had to be optimized. Pohl et al. [14] defined a Multi-Objective Genetic Algorithm for the Vehicle Routing Problem with Time Windows, where they defined new operators for the specific problem and optimized different risks, such as exceeding capacities and violating time windows. Rosenberg et al. [20] used NSGA-II to solve Intelligence, Surveillance and Reconnaissance (ISR) missions optimizing the latency, coverage, time, conflicts and cumulative military value. Finally, Stouch et al. [23] used coevolutionary algorithms to deal with a massive amount of objectives to optimize in the UAV routing problem.

3 CSPs for defining UAV Mission Planning

The MCMPP can be summed up in finding the correct schedule of resource-task assignments which satisfies the proposed constraints, similarly to CSPs. It can be defined as follows [2]:

- A set of variables $V = v_1, \dots, v_n$.
- For each variable, a finite set of possible values D_i (its domain).
- A set of constraints C_i restricting the values that variables can simultaneously take.

Then, the MCMPP [16] can be defined as a number n of **tasks**, $T = \{t_0, t_1, \dots, t_n\}$, performed by a team of (resources) m **UAVs**, $U = \{u_0, u_1, \dots, u_m\}$, at a specific time interval. Besides, each mission should be performed in a specific geographic zone. In addition, in this approach, there is a number l of **GCSs**, $G = \{g_0, g_1, \dots, g_l\}$, controlling these UAVs. A solution for a mission planning problem should be the assignment of each task to a specific UAV, and each UAV to a specific GCS, ensuring that the mission can be successfully performed.

There are different kind of tasks (e.g. photographing or escorting a target, monitoring a zone, etc.). Some of them could be Multi-UAV, i.e. they are performed by several UAVs (e.g. mapping an area, also called Step & Stare)

reducing the time needed to perform the task. Tasks can be carried out thanks to the sensors available (i.e. Electro-optical or Infra-red (EO/IR) cameras, Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), Maritime Patrol Radar (MPR), etc.) by the UAVs performing the mission. In addition, each task must be performed in a specific geographic *area* and in a specific *time interval*.

In Figure 1, a Mission Scenario with 7 tasks (represented in green), 5 UAVs and 2 GCSs is presented. As can be seen in this figure, the zone of the mission could contain some No Flight Zones (NFZs), represented in red. These zones must be avoided in the trajectories of the UAVs during the mission.

Fig. 1: Mission with 7 tasks (2 of them Multi-UAV), 5 UAVs and 2 GCSs.

Additionally, the vehicles performing the mission have some features that must be taken into account in order to check if a mission plan is correct: its **initial position**, its **initial fuel**, its **autonomy** or maximum flight time, its **range** or maximum flight distance, its **cost** per hour of usage, its **available sensors**, and one or more **flight profiles**. A vehicle's flight profile specifies at each moment its **speed**, its **fuel consumption ratio** and its **altitude**.

When a task is assigned to a vehicle, it is necessary to compute the **duration of the path** between the zone of the UAV's departure and the zone of the task start. If a task is the last one assigned to a vehicle, in addition, the **duration of the return** from this last task to the base must be calculated. In order to compute these durations, it is necessary to know which of the UAV's flight profiles will be used, providing the fuel consumption ratio, speed and

altitude as previously mentioned. For this reason, in these cases, the **flight profiles** used must also be **assigned** to solve the mission.

Finally, a mission could have some time and vehicle dependencies between different tasks. **Vehicle dependencies** consider if two tasks must be assigned the **same UAV** or **different UAVs**. Moreover, we consider **time dependencies** given by the **Allen's Interval Algebra** [1].

3.1 CSP Modelling

The MCMPP explained can be modelled using a CSP. First, we define which are the variables of the CSP and their domain. Then, we explain the different constraints considered for the MPP.

Looking at the assumptions explained so far in the previous section, the variables of the CSP that we have considered are as follows:

- **Assignments (*assign*) of tasks to UAVs**. As some tasks could be Multi-UAV, these variables are represented as a binary array of size $n \times m$. An assignment $assign[t, u] = 1$ means that task t is assigned to UAV u .
- **Orders (*order*)**, which define the order in which each UAV performs the tasks assigned to it. These variables are necessary when start and end times of tasks are not fixed, and they are represented as an array of size $n \times m$. Their domain is $[-1..n - 1]$, where -1 is only assigned when the UAV does not perform the task.
- **Assignments of UAVs to GCSs (*gcss*)**. There are m variables of this type, and their domain is $[-1..l - 1]$, where -1 is only assigned when the UAV is not assigned to any task.
- **Path Flight Profiles (*fpPath*)**, setting the flight profile that the vehicle must take for the path performance. These variables are represented as a $n \times m$ array, and their domains are the flight profiles of the UAV in the column: $fpPath[t, u] \in fps(u)$.
- **Return Flight Profiles (*fpReturn*)**, similar to the previous set of variables but for the return path of each UAV. There are m variables of this type, and their domain is the same as the previous variables: $fpReturn[u] \in fps(u)$.
- **Sensor used in the task performance (*sensTask*)**. These variables set the sensor of the vehicle that will be used during the task performance. It will be necessary to consider these variables just in the case that the vehicle performing the task has several sensors that could perform that task. These variables are represented as a $n \times m$ array, and their domains are the sensors of the task and UAV available for that assignment: $sensTask[t, u] \in sensors(t) \cap sensors(u)$.

On the other hand, there are some extra variables that will be computed during the propagation phase of the CSP. These variables are directly related to the variables presented before: *departure*, *durPath*, *start*, *durTask*, *end*,

$durLoiter$, $durReturn$, $returnTime$, $fuelPath$, $fuelTask$, $fuelLoiter$, $fuelReturn$, $distancePath$, $distanceTask$, $distanceLoiter$ and $distanceReturn$.

Now, we define the different constraints of the CSP, which consider all the specifications explained so far:

1. **Sensor constraints:** they check if a UAV has the sensor needed to perform its assigned tasks. Let $sensors(u)$ denote the sensors available for UAV u and $sensors(t)$ the sensors that could perform the task t then:

$$\forall t \in T \quad \forall u \in U \quad assign[t, u] = 1 \Rightarrow |sensors(t) \cap sensors(u)| > 0 \quad (5)$$

2. **Order constraints:** they assure that the values of the order variables are less than the number of tasks assigned to the UAV performing that task:

$$\forall t \in T \quad \forall u \in U \quad assign[t, u] = 1 \Rightarrow order[t, u] < \#\{\tau \in T | assign[\tau, u] = 1\} \quad (6)$$

and if two tasks are assigned to the same UAV, they have different orders:

$$\forall i, j \in T \quad \forall u \in U \quad assign[i, u] = assign[j, u] = 1 \Rightarrow order[i, u] \neq order[j, u] \quad (7)$$

3. **GCS constraints:** they assure that the GCSs assignments are correct. First, it is necessary to assure that the UAVs assigned to the GCS are of a type supported by that GCS (both in initial assignment and during tasks performance):

$$\forall u \in U \quad \forall g \in G \quad gcss[u] = g \Rightarrow type(u) \subset types(g) \quad (8)$$

Then, a constraint assures that the maximum number of UAVs that a GCS can handle is not overpassed at any moment:

$$\forall g \in G \quad \#\{u \in U | gcss[u] = g\} < maxNum(g) \quad (9)$$

Finally, it is necessary to check that GCS can cover the UAV during the mission:

$$\forall u \in U \quad \forall g \in G \quad gcss[u] = g \Rightarrow \forall t \in \mathbb{R} \quad distance(pos(u, t), pos_g) \leq coverage(g) \quad (10)$$

4. **Temporal constraints:** they assure the consistency of all the time variables considered. First, it is necessary to assure that the start time of the task equals the sum of the departure time and the duration for the path:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall t \in T \quad \forall u \in U \quad assign[t, u] = 1 \Rightarrow \\ departure[t, u] + durPath[t, u] = start[t, u] \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

and that end time is the sum of the start time and the duration of the task:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall t \in T \quad \forall u \in U \quad assign[t, u] = 1 \Rightarrow \\ start[t, u] + durTask[t, u] = end[t, u] \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Then, the duration of the path is computed as the distance traversed in the path divided by the speed given by the path flight profile:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall t \in T \quad \forall u \in U \quad assign[t, u] = 1 \Rightarrow \\ durPath[t, u] = \frac{distancePath[t, u]}{speed(fpPath[t, u])} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

If tasks have fixed start and end times, then it is necessary to compute the duration of the loiter as the difference between the end of a task and the departure for its consecutive task:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall i, j \in T \quad \forall u \in U \quad assign[i, u] = assign[j, u] = 1 \\ \wedge \quad order[i, u] = order[j, u] - 1 \Rightarrow \\ durLoiter[j, u] = departure[j, u] - end[i, u] \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

On the other hand, the duration of the return is computed as the distance traversed in the return path divided by the speed given by the return flight profile:

$$\forall u \in U \quad durReturn[u] = \frac{distanceReturn[u]}{speed(fpReturn[u])} \quad (15)$$

Once we have computed the return path duration, we can compute the return time as the sum of the end of the last task performed by the UAV and the return duration:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall t \in T \quad \forall u \in U \quad assign[t, u] = 1 \\ \wedge \quad order[t, u] = \#\{\tau \in T \mid assign[\tau, u] = 1\} - 1 \Rightarrow \\ returnTime[u] = end[t, u] - durReturn[u] \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Finally, it is necessary to assure that two tasks that collide in time are never assigned to the same UAV:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall i, j \in T \quad \forall u \in U \quad & assign[i, u] = assign[j, u] = 1 \\ & \wedge order[i, u] < order[j, u] \Rightarrow \\ & end[i, u] \leq departure[j, u] \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

5. **Dependency Constraints:** these constraints are related to the time and vehicle dependencies mentioned before. The time dependency constraints, based on Allen's Interval Algebra [1], for each pair of tasks i and j , assuming $\forall i, j \in T \quad \forall u \in U \quad assign[i, u] = assign[j, u] = 1$, are as follow:

$$i < j \Rightarrow end[i, u] \leq start[j, u] \quad (18)$$

$$i \ m \ j \Rightarrow end[i, u] = start[j, u] \quad (19)$$

$$i \ o \ j \Rightarrow \begin{cases} start[i, u] \leq start[j, u] \\ end[i, u] \geq start[j, u] \\ end[i, u] \leq end[j, u] \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

$$i \ s \ j \Rightarrow \begin{cases} start[i, u] = start[j, u] \\ end[i, u] \leq end[j, u] \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

$$i \ d \ j \Rightarrow \begin{cases} start[i, u] \geq start[j, u] \\ end[i, u] \leq end[j, u] \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

$$i \ f \ j \Rightarrow \begin{cases} start[i, u] \geq start[j, u] \\ end[i, u] = end[j, u] \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

$$i = j \Rightarrow \begin{cases} start[i, u] = start[j, u] \\ end[i, u] = end[j, u] \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

On the other hand, vehicle dependencies imply the following constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall i, j \in T \quad & sameUAV(i, j) \Rightarrow \\ \forall u \in U \quad & assign[i, u] = assign[j, u] \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \forall i, j \in T \quad & diffUAV(i, j) \Rightarrow \\ \forall u \in U \quad & assign[i, u] \neq assign[j, u] \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

6. **Autonomy constraints:** they assure that the total flight time for each vehicle is less than its autonomy:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall u \in U \quad flightTime[u] &= \sum_{\substack{t \in T \\ assign[t]=u}} (durPath[t] \\ &+ durTask[t] + durLoiter[u]) + durReturn[u] \\ &< autonomy(u) \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

7. **Distance constraints:** they assure that the distance traversed by each vehicle is less than its range:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall u \in U \quad distance[u] &= \sum_{\substack{t \in T \\ assign[t]=u}} (distancePath[t] \\ &+ distanceTask[t] + distanceLoiter[u]) \\ &+ distanceReturn[u] < range(u) \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

To compute these distances, we have used GeographicLib¹ for the computation of distance and points in Geographic coordinates; and Theta* [4] to perform a path between these points avoiding No Flight Zones (NFZ) and terrain obstacles. The elevation of the terrain has been read from DTED maps using GDAL².

8. **Fuel constraints:** they assure that the fuel consumed by each vehicle is less than its initial fuel $fuel_u$:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall u \in U \quad fuel[u] &= \sum_{\substack{t \in T \\ assign[t]=u}} (fuelPath[t] + fuelTask[t] \\ &+ fuelLoiter[t] + fuelReturn[u]) < fuel(u) \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Each one of these fuel consumptions is computed as the product of its associated duration and fuel consumption ratio. For example, the fuel consumption for the path is computed multiplying the fuel consumption ratio given by the path flight profile and the duration of the path:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall t \in T \quad \forall u \in U \quad assign[t, u] = 1 &\Rightarrow fuelPath[t, u] \\ &= durPath[t, u] \times fuelRatio(fpPath[t, u]) \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

¹ <http://geographiclib.sourceforge.net/>

² <http://www.gdal.org/>

4 Proposed MOGA-CSP Algorithm

To deal with the huge amount of constraints and the big search space of the problem, a hybrid approach based on MOGA and CSP is proposed for the MCMPP. In our approach, the CSP is considered inside the fitness function of the MOGA, checking that the solutions fulfil all the constraints. When a solution does not fulfil some constraint, the number of constraints checked until fail in the propagation phase of the CSP is used as a weighted penalty function in order to reproduce the solutions fulfilling the highest number of constraints. This methodology will help the algorithm to converge faster when the space of solutions is very small compared to the search space, causing the randomly generated initial population to, maybe, not reach any valid solution.

4.1 Encoding

The encoding of this new approach consists of six different alleles representing the features described in the previous section. These alleles are divided into three groups according to their applicability of operators:

1. The first group of alleles is composed of three alleles of size n each one:
 - **UAVs assigned to each task.**
 - **Flight profiles used for each UAV to each assigned task.**
 - **Sensors used for the task performance** by each UAV.

If the T_i task is Multi-UAV, then the corresponding cell of each allele contains a vector representing the different UAVs, flight profiles or sensors assigned to this task. In Figure 2, an example of this group for a mission with 5 tasks and 3 UAVs is presented. Min refers to Minimum Consumption Profile, max to Max Speed Profile, mR to MPR, sR to SAR, iR to Inverse Synthetic Aperture Radar (ISAR) and eiS to EO/IR Sensor. In the reproduction phase of the algorithm, a 2-point crossover and an uniform mutation is applied to this group of alleles.

UAV					FpPath					SensUsed				
T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅
1	3	1	2	3	max	min	max	min	max	mR	sR	mR	iR	eiS
3			3		min			min		sR			sR	

Fig. 2: Example of the first group of alleles from an individual representing a possible solution for a problem with 5 tasks and 3 UAVs.

2. The second group is composed of an allele representing the **permutation of the task orders**. As described in a previous approach [15], these values are used to indicate the order in which each UAV performs the tasks

assigned to it. It is only used if there are several tasks assigned to the same UAV. In Figure 3 an example of this allele is presented, which together with the first allele (assignments) of Figure 2 shows that UAV 1 performs tasks 1 and 3 in this order; UAV 2 performs task 4; and UAV 3 performs tasks 5, 2, 1 and 4. The permutation constraints the values of genes to be different and in the range 0 to $n - 1$. In the reproduction phase, a Partially-Matched Crossover (PMX) and an Insert Mutation is applied to this allele.

Order				
T₁	T₂	T₃	T₄	T₅
2	1	3	4	0
Permutation				

Fig. 3: Example of the second group of alleles from an individual representing a possible solution for a problem with 5 tasks and 3 UAVs.

- The third group of alleles is composed of two alleles of size m each one:
 - **GCSs controlling each UAV.**
 - **Flight Profiles used by each UAV to return** to the base.

In Figure 4, an example of this group for a mission with 3 UAVs and 2 GCSs is presented. In the reproduction phase of the algorithm, a 2-point crossover and an uniform mutation is applied to this group of alleles.

GCS			FpReturn		
U₁	U₂	U₃	U₁	U₂	U₃
2	2	1	max	min	max

Fig. 4: Example of the third group of alleles from an individual representing a possible solution for a problem with 3 UAVs and 2 GCSs.

4.2 Fitness Function

The fitness function of the algorithm considers a CSP modelling of the problem in order to check that all constraints are fulfilled for a given solution.

In a previous approach [17], when a solution was invalid, the number of constraints fulfilled before the failure of some invalid constraint was considered. In this approach, if the population is filled with no valid solution, then the solutions satisfying the highest number of constraints are considered for next generation. For the experimentation, we will call this algorithm MOGA-CSP-Valid.

In this work, we consider a new approach where instead of counting the number of constraints fulfilled until fail, we force the CSP to check all the constraints and return the exact number of invalid constraints. In this way, we expect that the algorithm will converge faster. One inconvenient is that the runtime of each generation will increase respect to the previous approach, but we expect that the number of generations needed to converge will decrease much more, so the total runtime will be lower. For the experiments, we will call this new approach MOGA-CSP-Invalid.

On the other hand, when a solution is valid, so all constraints are fulfilled, then the fitness works as a multi-objective function minimizing the objectives of the problem:

- The **total cost** of the mission.
- The end time of the mission or **makespan**.
- The **risk** of the mission, which is computed as an average percentage indicating how risky the mission is. We consider three risk factors: UAVs that finish the mission with low fuel, UAVs that fly near to the ground and UAVs that fly close between them.
- The **number of UAVs** used in the mission.
- The **total fuel consumption**.
- The **total flight time**.
- The **total distance traversed**.

4.3 Algorithm

Algorithm 1 shows this new approach presented so far. Lines 8-15 show the implementation of the fitness function previously explained. The buildArchive function used by NSGA-II approach [5] is used in order to select the best solutions of the Pareto Front (Line 16). Then, the best elitist individuals are selected and passed to the next generation (Line 21) and a tournament wheel selection over these N individuals (Line 23) selects those that will be applied the genetic operators.

Next, we use a proper crossover operator (Line 24), consisting of a specific crossover operation for each group of the alleles of the representation, as explained in section 4.1 Then, a mutation operator (Lines 25-26) will be applied depending on a probability P_m . This mutation operator, as well as the crossover, consists of a specific mutation for each group of alleles of the encoding.

Finally, the stopping criteria designed for this algorithm compares the non dominated solutions obtained so far at each generation with the solutions from the previous generation (Lines 17-20). If the solutions from a previous generation remains unchangeable for a number of generations, then the algorithm will stop and return these solutions as an approximation of the POF.

Algorithm 1: Guided MOGA-CSP algorithm for MCMPPs

Input: A mission $M = (T, U, G)$ where T is a set of tasks to perform denoted by $\{t_1, \dots, t_n\}$, U is a set of UAVs denoted by $\{u_1, \dots, u_m\}$ and G is a set of GCSs denoted by $\{g_1, \dots, g_i\}$. The set of objectives O and their upper bounds $\bar{M} = \{M_i \gg \text{avg}(o_i)\}$. And positive numbers *generations*, *population*, μ , λ , *mutprobability* and *stopGeneration*

Output: POF obtained with best solutions

```

1  $S \leftarrow$  randomly generated set of population of  $p$  chromosomes
2  $i \leftarrow 1$ 
3  $convergence \leftarrow 0$ 
4  $pof \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
5 while  $i \leq generations \wedge convergence < stopGenerations$  do
6    $newS \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
7    $F \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
8   for  $j \leftarrow 1$  to  $p$  do
9      $[valid, numInvalidConstraints] = CSP_{Check}(S_j)$ 
10     $Fit \leftarrow newFitness()$ 
11     $Fit.valid \leftarrow valid$  if  $valid$  then
12       $Fit.objectives \leftarrow MultiObjectiveFitness(S_j)$ 
13    else
14       $Fit.numInvalid \leftarrow numValidConstraints$ 
15     $F \leftarrow F \cup Fit$ 
16   $S \leftarrow buildNSGA2Archive(S, \lambda)$ 
17   $newpof \leftarrow createPOF(S)$ 
18  if  $newpof = pof$  then
19     $convergence \leftarrow convergence + 1$ 
20   $pof = newpof$ 
21   $newS \leftarrow SelectElites(S, \mu)$ 
22  for  $j \leftarrow \mu$  to  $\lambda$  do
23     $p1, p2 \leftarrow TournamentSelection(S)$ 
24     $i1, i2 \leftarrow Crossover(p1, p2)$ 
25     $i1 \leftarrow Mutation(i1, mutprobability)$ 
26     $i2 \leftarrow Mutation(i2, mutprobability)$ 
27     $newS \leftarrow newS \cup \{i1, i2\}$ 
28   $S \leftarrow S \cup newS$ 
29   $i \leftarrow i + 1$ 
30 return  $pof$ 

```

5 Experimental Results

In order to test this new approach, 16 Mission Scenarios have been designed (see Table 1). Each scenario is identified by an ID with two digits, where the first digit indicates the complexity, being 1 the less complex scenarios and 4 the most complex ones. In each scenario, tasks, UAVs, GCSs and NFZs are scattered throughout the map. Each UAV has different sensors and each task can be performed by different set of sensors, so there are several possible solutions. On the other hand, each UAV has been set with a different amount of initial fuel. The increasing complexity of these datasets allows us to compare how this new approach behaves according to the complexity of the problem.

Table 1: Features of the different datasets designed.

Dataset Id.	Tasks	Multi-UAV Tasks	UAVs	GCSs	NFZs	Time Dependencies
1.1	5	0	3	1	0	0
1.2	6	1	3	1	1	0
1.3	6	1	4	2	2	1
1.4	7	1	5	2	1	2
2.1	8	2	5	2	3	1
2.2	9	2	5	2	0	2
2.3	9	2	6	2	2	2
2.4	10	2	6	2	3	3
3.1	11	3	6	2	3	2
3.2	12	3	7	3	0	2
3.3	12	3	8	3	2	3
3.4	13	4	7	3	4	4
4.1	14	4	8	3	0	3
4.2	15	4	9	3	5	4
4.3	16	4	9	3	4	4
4.4	16	5	10	3	5	5

The new MOGA-CSP-Invalid approach is compared against a common MOGA-CSP approach (with no guidance at all) and the previous MOGA-CSP-Valid approach. To setup the MOGA of both approaches, the selection criteria ($\mu + \lambda$) used was $100 + 1000$, where λ is the number of offspring (population size), and μ the elitism size, i.e. the number of the best parents that survive from current generation to the next. The mutation probability is 10%, and the number of generations used in the stopping criteria is 20, combined with a maximum number of generations of 1000. Each problem is run 20 times, extracting for each execution the number of generations needed to converge, the hypervolume metric [27] of the solutions obtained and the runtime. Results are shown in Tables 2 (number of generations), 3 (hypervolume with the normalized optimization variables) and 4 (runtime). The experiments have been run in an Intel Core i5-6200 2.3 GHz with 8 cores and 16GB DDR3 RAM.

It can be seen that in these tables that the hypervolumes are similar in datasets with low or medium complexity, but in those with high complexity it can be seen that the MOGA-CSP approach does not converge, so the hypervolume is pretty lower (see Figure 6). On the other hand, the number of generations needed to converge decrease in the MOGA-CSP-Invalid approach respect to the MOGA-CSP-Valid approach specially on highly complex datasets (see Figure 5). In addition, looking at the results of the runtime table, it is appreciable that for lower complexity datasets, the runtime of MOGA-CSP-Invalid is higher than MOGA-CSP-Valid, but for high complex datasets, it is clearly lower (see Figure 7). With this, we can say that forcing the CSP to check all constraints and considering the number of invalid constraints as a heuristic decreases the convergence time specially for highly complex Missions.

Table 2: Average and standard deviation of the Number of generations until convergence for the MOGA-CSP, the MOGA-CSP-Valid and the new MOGA-CSP-Invalid approach.

Dataset Id.	MOGA-CSP	MOGA-CSP-Valid	MOGA-CSP-Invalid
1.1	23.5 ± 12.3	22.6 ± 13.4	24.3 ± 12.6
1.2	35.8 ± 15.6	37.4 ± 12.8	36.9 ± 14.5
1.3	55.2 ± 14.7	54.1 ± 15.3	54.3 ± 14.9
1.4	97.6 ± 18.3	90.1 ± 19.9	89.9 ± 17.7
2.1	142.5 ± 22.2	123.0 ± 20.4	120.4 ± 22.9
2.2	194.5 ± 25.3	164.7 ± 24.2	155.8 ± 24.1
2.3	263.5 ± 28.7	210.2 ± 25.4	196.5 ± 23.3
2.4	357.8 ± 33.2	279.6 ± 28.3	254.1 ± 26.6
3.1	485.2 ± 38.3	369.5 ± 31.2	315.2 ± 25.7
3.2	634.4 ± 45.6	491.6 ± 33.6	405.6 ± 27.2
3.3	805.2 ± 68.3	587.0 ± 35.8	476.2 ± 29.4
3.4	915.3 ± 73.4	649.1 ± 36.1	534.3 ± 30.9
4.1	982.8 ± 20.5	776.4 ± 40.9	598.5 ± 31.2
4.2	998.4 ± 5.6	852.8 ± 46.7	634.9 ± 33.6
4.3	1000.0 ± 0.0	923.7 ± 51.4	678.5 ± 32.5
4.4	1000.0 ± 0.0	958.4 ± 56.2	713.2 ± 34.9

Fig. 5: Average Number of generations until convergence for the approaches and datasets proposed.

6 Conclusions

In this paper, we have presented a hybrid approach based on MOGA and CSP for the MCMPP problem. The MOGA-CSP approach is able to solve

Table 3: Average and standard deviation of Hypervolume for the MOGA-CSP, the MOGA-CSP-Valid and the new MOGA-CSP-Invalid approach.

Dataset Id.	MOGA-CSP	MOGA-CSP-Valid	MOGA-CSP-Invalid
1.1	0.895 ± 0.000	0.895 ± 0.000	0.895 ± 0.000
1.2	0.923 ± 0.000	0.923 ± 0.000	0.923 ± 0.000
1.3	0.979 ± 0.005	0.979 ± 0.006	0.979 ± 0.004
1.4	1.032 ± 0.013	1.032 ± 0.011	1.032 ± 0.008
2.1	1.095 ± 0.022	1.097 ± 0.031	1.097 ± 0.041
2.2	1.125 ± 0.033	1.126 ± 0.036	1.131 ± 0.042
2.3	1.543 ± 0.056	1.675 ± 0.044	1.698 ± 0.063
2.4	1.978 ± 0.092	1.986 ± 0.096	2.003 ± 0.093
3.1	2.254 ± 0.103	2.348 ± 0.087	2.352 ± 0.075
3.2	2.985 ± 0.123	3.129 ± 0.098	3.134 ± 0.103
3.3	3.548 ± 0.112	3.766 ± 0.102	3.799 ± 0.087
3.4	4.097 ± 0.234	4.342 ± 0.134	4.354 ± 0.122
4.1	4.154 ± 0.547	4.678 ± 0.197	4.843 ± 0.114
4.2	4.145 ± 1.234	4.978 ± 0.334	5.123 ± 0.154
4.3	4.082 ± 1.478	5.127 ± 0.778	5.780 ± 0.235
4.4	4.123 ± 1.554	4.864 ± 1.754	6.534 ± 0.456

Fig. 6: Average Hypervolume obtained for the approaches and datasets proposed.

Multi-UAV Mission Planning Problems with different (increasing) complexities under different mission situations (modifying critical features as the number of available UAVs, GCSs, No Flight Zones or Time Dependencies). The presented approach considers missions consisting of several tasks to be performed by

Table 4: Average and standard deviation of Runtime (in minutes) for the MOGA-CSP, the MOGA-CSP-Valid and the new MOGA-CSP-Invalid approach.

Dataset Id.	MOGA-CSP	MOGA-CSP-Valid	MOGA-CSP-Invalid
1.1	0.6 ± 0.3	0.5 ± 0.4	1.3 ± 0.8
1.2	2.4 ± 0.6	2.9 ± 0.4	3.8 ± 1.2
1.3	5.7 ± 1.3	5.2 ± 1.4	7.2 ± 2.1
1.4	8.6 ± 2.1	7.9 ± 2.2	9.9 ± 2.8
2.1	12.0 ± 3.6	10.9 ± 3.3	15.6 ± 4.7
2.2	18.8 ± 5.1	15.3 ± 4.8	25.3 ± 6.2
2.3	26.7 ± 7.2	21.2 ± 6.6	31.7 ± 7.9
2.4	39.1 ± 10.8	30.8 ± 9.2	37.4 ± 11.2
3.1	54.4 ± 14.7	44.5 ± 11.0	45.6 ± 13.9
3.2	96.3 ± 19.6	67.4 ± 14.2	62.1 ± 19.2
3.3	201.2 ± 22.3	88.2 ± 17.7	75.8 ± 22.2
3.4	378.3 ± 44.5	134.3 ± 20.7	102.5 ± 25.5
4.1	459.9 ± 24.6	279.4 ± 26.4	207.6 ± 27.5
4.2	506.6 ± 15.3	365.6 ± 29.1	253.9 ± 30.3
4.3	556.0 ± 6.6	458.9 ± 32.9	304.5 ± 32.8
4.4	598.1 ± 8.3	507.2 ± 38.2	365.2 ± 36.2

Fig. 7: Average runtime obtained for the approaches and datasets proposed.

several UAVs using a specific sensor. Each UAV is controlled by a GCS and use specific Flight Profiles. The problem has been modelled as a CSP considering the assignments of tasks to UAVs, the orders of tasks, the assignments of UAVs to GCSs, the sensors used for each task, the flight profiles used by each UAV in

its path to each assigned task and the return flight profile used by each UAV as variables; and several constraints involving these variables. On the other hand, the encoding of the MOGA considers the same variables as the CSP. A new fitness function has been designed for this approach: first the solution is checked with the CSP model and if it is invalid, the number of constraints fulfilled is used to guide the search of solutions in the following generations; otherwise, a multi-objective fitness function optimizing several objectives is considered.

The experiments performed over several missions show that this new approach outperforms the results obtained previously in terms of convergence time for complex problems with huge search space and reduced solution space. Nevertheless, these results could be outperformed combining other new methodologies with this one, which we will next investigate.

Future works will focus on developing a Decision Support System (DSS) for this problem, in order to select one solution among those obtained by the algorithm according to some quality metrics and the GCS operator profile.

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